

Detection of thermal anomalies on building façades using infrared thermography and supervised learning

Braulio Barahona, Roger Buck, Oskar Okaya, Philipp Schuetz

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences, Technikumstrasse 21, 6048 Horw, Switzerland

E-mail: braulio.barahonagarzon@hslu.ch

Abstract. We propose a cost-effective, non-intrusive approach to assess the quality of the thermal isolation of the building stock in a given municipality or small city. Our prototype measurement system, mounted on a vehicle, acquires geotagged optical and infrared images from the street-side of the buildings. A basic approach to detect gross thermal anomalies, such as thermal bridges, via a binary classifier trained on carefully labeled infrared images is demonstrated. Thermal anomalies are identified with a precision score of around 89.2 % and 75.6 % recall on a test dataset of 1184 images infrared recorded in Hergiswil (NW). The enabled automated assessment helps to identify retrofitting targets and supports increasing the renovation rate.

1. Introduction

Infrared thermography (IRT) is widely used to study the thermal properties of buildings. It has the benefit that it can be performed at a distance, in a non-intrusive way. One application is to find energy related defects in buildings, such as thermal bridges which lead to energy losses. Façade surface or insulation areas with excessive heat losses or moisture transfer phenomena can also be identified with IRT [1]. As such, IRT can facilitate cost-effective evaluation of the thermal condition of buildings. However, the acquisition of thermal images as it applies to energy audits [1, 2] requires careful consideration of the environmental conditions, and the objects in the field of view of the camera to avoid artefacts. Moreover, analyses of the images require expert judgement to properly identify defects. Early attempts to automate acquisition and analyses include the use mobile systems on vehicles combined with 3D buildings models [3, 4] or with laser scanners [5]. Combining the information of the 3D structure with the image facilitates segmentation of the façade and in turn the detection of thermal leakages. Another approach proposed in [6] is the use of drones to acquire images from different angles of a given building. More recently, the possibility of estimating qualitative properties of the building envelope with IRT and drones was reported in [7]. In terms of processing, in [8], the application of a series of filters and thresholding algorithms to detect thermal anomalies in infrared images acquired by a drone was described. An example of water leakage in a reinforced concrete beam, a case of a roof with evident debonding of the roof substrates, and an image with windows and air conditioners were used to test the prototyped algorithm. An application of supervised classification was shown by [9] where IRT and laser scanner data were used to detect windows and doors on two building

façades. Their approach makes use of features extracted from geometry, color, and infrared data to train a random forest classifier. Here, we describe a prototype system for acquisition of thermal and optical images, and apply a linear model to distinguish between buildings that look thermally well insulated versus those that show anomalies. Optical images are used to support image annotation, the supervised classification is performed on infrared images only. Our aim is to explore the scalability of IRT to assess the thermal envelope of buildings in municipalities or small cities in a cost-effective manner.

2. Data acquisition

Prototypes of a mobile measurement system that can acquire optical, infrared images, and geolocation data are built with different sensors and acquisition via a small single board computer. Here, data from our high-resolution prototype (p2 in Figure 1) based on a commercial camera (Duo Pro R) is presented. It combines an uncooled microbolometer with a 640 x 512 pixel resolution for thermal imaging and an optical sensor with 4000 x 3000 pixel resolution. The p2 prototype includes a global positioning system (GPS) receiver, and is enclosed in a water-resistant case that can be mounted on the top of a car to enable efficient acquisition of images of buildings as seen from the street, perpendicularly to driving direction.

First datasets of building façades are collected in the communities of Horw (LU) and Hergiswil (NW), where p2 records video at a frame rate of 30 Hz while the car is driven around in urban areas of the municipalities. Measurements campaigns are conducted during the winter season. Times are carefully chosen to minimize artefacts due to direct sunlight, snow, humidity, and to ensure a high difference between indoor and outdoor temperatures. The route of one measurement campaign in Hergiswil is shown in Figure 1. The recorded raw radiometric data, optical images, and metadata including geolocation are parsed and verified by visual inspection. Plausibility checks, when needed, are performed with the support of publicly available data. A prototype of a visualization tool is developed to aid with such verification and data consolidation tasks. It also serves as a tool to communicate interesting cases to stakeholders. It is implemented in the framework of google earth exploiting the possibilities of integrated presentation with geo-referenced data. A snapshot is shown in Figure 1 where it is illustrated that Google street data and satellite imagery are useful to verify our images and geotags, identify obvious changes and get other angles or areas outside the field of view of our sensors. The federal register of buildings and dwellings (RBD¹) is used to obtain metadata about the building, such as type of house, size, year of construction, year of last renovation, etc. Also, information about the heating system is available for a share of the Swiss building stock. On this basis, we implement a supervised learning approach to classify images into healthy and anomalous as described in Section 3. Examples of a thermally healthy house, and one with a thermal bridge are shown in Figure 2 where the thermal image on the right shows two clear streaks across the façade in the horizontal direction. These indicate higher infrared radiation relative to other areas of the wall, which is associated to heat losses. Given the location and shape of the streaks, and the meta information about the image, it clearly indicates a thermal bridge between the indoor space, the structure of the building, and the outdoors space.

3. Methods: detection of anomalies with a binary classifier

3.1. Framing of the problem and data curation

Supervised learning requires a set of N examples $\{(\mathbf{X}, Y)_i\}_{i=1}^N$, where $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{X}$ is an input vector, in our case a thermal image, and $y_i \in Y$ is a label describing the category that image belongs to. Once the input data \mathbf{X} is consolidated and verified, annotation of each image \mathbf{x}_i is performed to attribute the corresponding label y_i . Data is consolidated by creating a table that maps optical

¹ <https://www.housing-stat.ch/de/madd.html>

Figure 1. Top right: hardware prototypes p0 and p2 for acquisition of geotagged images. p2 is based on a Duo Pro R from FLIR, Willsonville, U.S.A. Background: route followed when acquiring images with p2 in Hergiswil in November 2020. Left: snapshot of visualization tool for verification of our images with google street data and satellite imagery. As shown with data from RBD, the building in this example was built in 1950 and it has 4 floors. The address and identification number are blurred to protect privacy.

Figure 2. Optical and thermal images illustrating a thermal bridge (right) and a ventilation system that might be wrongly perceived as a defect (left).

and thermal data to time stamps and GPS tags. For the verification, first we filter out images such as those that do not contain buildings, have excessive foreground objects, or large share of background or artefacts that make it difficult to judge defects. GPS tags are then verified for a couple of points to ensure that the whole route is well recorded. More detailed verification is done on a case-by-case basis when the human expert requires more information to annotate the thermal image, such as the case of ventilation components (e.g. left of Figure 2) or open windows (e.g. Figure 3).

Since annotating the images is extremely time consuming, we define a taxonomy of objects to be identified within an image. Namely, only four categories are explicitly annotated (*Roof*, *Components*, *Wall*, and *Defect*), the binary labels are then inferred according to this taxonomy: $y = \{\mathbf{no\ defect}, \mathbf{defect}\}$. The annotation process is done in two steps in order to minimize errors. First, by visual inspection each image is categorized as either *No Defect*, *Defect*, or *no building*. Aligned optical images are used for support. In a second step, images categorized as *No Defect*, and *Defect* are annotated one by one to indicate the size and location of anomalies, if any, and other objects according to the taxonomy. Figure 3 illustrates this step, where areas are marked and the assigned categories are indicated. As mentioned before, optical images and other data is used to minimize mistakes and solve difficult examples as those ones shown in Figures 2 and 3. The final label $y_i \in Y$ is then assigned after this careful examination of the individual thermal image \mathbf{x}_i .

Figure 3. Illustration of the image annotation process. Four categories of objects annotated with the tool VIA [10], then the binary labels for training are extracted.

3.2. Binary classifier with hinge loss

We apply a linear model to distinguish between **defect** and **no defect** images. This means that the decision boundary is given by $\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x} + b = 0$ which is a hyperplane in the feature space given by the dimension of the input vector. The standard formulation of this problem is to minimize the Euclidean norm $\|\mathbf{w}\|$ subject to $y_i(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x}_i - b) - 1 = 0$. An addition to make this algorithm less sensitive to noise that might make the two classes not linearly separable, is the use of the hinge loss $\max(0, 1 - y_i(\mathbf{w}\mathbf{x}_i - b))$ and $\|\mathbf{w}\|$ for regularization term as the cost function. Optimal parameters \mathbf{w}^* and b^* are then obtained with stochastic gradient descent. This is a common approach to efficiently tackle classification problems with large number of examples N and features $|\mathbf{x}_i|$. Implementations are taken from the scikit-learn [11] software tool kit.

We train this classifier on the IRT data rendered as RGB images to feed the algorithm with the same representation as the human expert uses for annotation. This gives us a large number of features $\dim(\mathbf{x}_i) = n \times m \times c = 98.304 \times 10^4$ where $n \times m$ is the resolution of the microbolometer and $c = 3$ the number of color channels in the rendered image (i.e. red, green, blue in RGB color model). Therefore, a first test of the viability of this approach is done on a small subset of the dataset, we then proceed with standard training steps as described in the following section.

4. Results and discussion

Data collected in Hergiswil (Section 2 and Figures 1 to 3) are curated following the steps in Section 3.1 to obtain a dataset of $N = 3184$ labeled examples only with a small class imbalance. Namely, approximately 4 out of 10 images are labeled **defect**, corresponding to 20 buildings amongst an estimate of 600 within the scope of this measurement campaign. Although this dataset is relatively small for computer vision tasks, compared to other works using IRT for assessing the thermal envelope of buildings, it is a relatively large dataset with high resolution. Given that the feature space is also large, a first step to test the viability of our approach is to perform several train-test runs in random, small subsets of the dataset. We perform train and test 30 times in different random subsets of $N = 300$ images and obtain accuracy scores of in the order of 73 %. These are encouraging results as training time is in the order of 2 minutes and the accuracy value well above the random guess.

To evaluate how well the algorithm generalizes we apply 10-fold cross-validation to study how the performance changes with different train dataset size. Thus, the training and validation is performed on the training dataset by splitting the dataset in 10 folds, training in 9 of them and using using the remaining, distinct, fold for validation each time. Experiments with data sets of size $N_{train} = \{500, 1000, 2000\}$ yield mean validation scores of 76.8 %, 83.0 %, and 84.5 % accuracy with 5.6 %, 5.2 %, and 4.9 % standard deviation.

Finally, we split the dataset into training (2000 images) and testing set (1384 images). This split is made at random, instead of stratified sampling, because we expect this to reflect closer our field application case. The trade-off between precision and recall is illustrated by the precision and recall versus classifier threshold curve, and the ROC curve in Figure 4. These curves show how precision, recall (or TPR), and false positive rate (FPR) change as the threshold of the decision function is changed on a set of predictions already calculated with a classifier threshold equal to zero. The results from the test set are shown in the confusion matrix in Figure 4. We observe that when **defect** is predicted the algorithm is correct 89.2 % of the time (precision metric, 332 correct out of 372) and that from the 439 images with the true label **defect** in this test data set of 1184 images, around 75.6 % of them were correctly estimated (recall metric, 332 out of 439). F1-score is 0.819 and area under the curve (AUC) is 0.851.

Figure 4. From left to right: precision and recall at different classification thresholds, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, and confusion matrix. Confusion matrix labels $\{0, 1\}$ correspond to $\{\mathbf{no\ defect}, \mathbf{defect}\}$.

This model reached a good trade-off between precision and recall. Further improvements, particularly to the recall metric, will be explored with more data and more advanced algorithms such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs). When automating this anomaly detection task, an important aspect to consider in the future, is that the raw data would include a larger variety of classes. Thereby the classification performance is expected to deteriorate in such case. Nevertheless, linear models can also be applied to classify multiple classes by framing the problem into multiple binary classification subproblems. Other approaches such as CNNs can be directly framed to classify multiple classes. Therefore, the baseline results presented here can be extended to our aim.

5. Conclusion and outlook

We demonstrate the application of infrared thermography to automatically detect thermal anomalies, particularly thermal bridges. The data are recorded with our acquisition system based on a commercial infrared camera. Data preprocessing and annotation workflows for supervised learning are set up to facilitate the training of a linear model for binary classification of **defect** or **no defect** images. On a data set of 3184 thermal images from Hergiswil (NW), the linear model

scores 89.2 % precision and 75.6 % recall on 1184 test images. These results serve as a baseline for more advanced approaches, such as those in the field of semantic segmentation. Another development path on sight is the evaluation of the viability to compute the thermal anomaly detection on the device, and to transmit the results to a central application for visualization. In terms of extracting information from our sensor data and other data sources, important future steps are: detection of different types of anomalies, and quantification of heat losses. We think such tools and methods can enable a cost-efficient identification of buildings with increased heat losses or gross thermal defects, within a large geographical area. This methodology could help facility managers, as well as communal officers to quickly identify renovation targets with a high impact on the reduction of primary energy consumption.

Acknowledgments

This research is supported by the Swiss Commission for technology and innovation under contract number 34747.1 IP- EE.

References

- [1] Lucchi E 2018 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **82** 3077–3090
- [2] Dall’O G, Sarto L, Panza A *et al.* 2013 *Energies* **6** 3859–3878
- [3] Hoegner L and Stilla U 2009 Thermal leakage detection on building facades using infrared textures generated by mobile mapping *Joint Urban Remote Sensing Event* (IEEE) pp 1–6
- [4] Sirmacek B, Hoegner L and Stilla U 2011 An automatic system to detect thermal leakages and damages on building facade using thermal images *Joint Urban Remote Sensing Event* pp 1–4 URL <https://elib.dlr.de/67807/>
- [5] Fernández-Llorca D, García Lorente A, Fernández C, Garcia Daza I and Sotelo M 2013 Automatic thermal leakage detection in building facades using laser and thermal images *International Conference on Computer Aided Systems Theory* (Springer) pp 71–78
- [6] Mauriello M L and Froehlich J E 2014 Towards automated thermal profiling of buildings at scale using unmanned aerial vehicles and 3d-reconstruction *ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing: Adjunct Publication* pp 119–122
- [7] Bayomi N, Nagpal S, Rakha T and Fernandez J E 2021 *Energy and Buildings* **233** 110648
- [8] De Filippo M, Asadiabadi S, Ko N and Sun H 2019 Concept of computer vision based algorithm for detecting thermal anomalies in reinforced concrete structures *The 15th International Workshop on Advanced Infrared Technology and Applications* vol 27 (MDPI) ISSN 2504-3900 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2504-3900/27/1/18>
- [9] Jarzabek-Rychard M, Lin D and Maas H G 2020 *Remote Sensing* **12** ISSN 2072-4292 URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/12/3/543>
- [10] Dutta A and Zisserman A 2019 The VIA annotation software for images, audio and video *MM ’19: The 27th ACM International Conference on Multimedia* (New York, NY, USA: ACM) ISBN 978-1-4503-6889-6/19/10 URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3343031.3350535>
- [11] Pedregosa F, Varoquaux G, Gramfort A, Michel V, Thirion B, Grisel O, Blondel M, Prettenhofer P, Weiss R, Dubourg V, Vanderplas J, Passos A, Cournapeau D, Brucher M, Perrot M and Duchesnay E 2011 *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **12** 2825–2830